

Functioning of Public Health Administration in Bihar

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Abstract: The functioning of public health administration in Bihar was investigated during the period September 2013 to August 2015. A mixed method was adopted to study the manner they accomplished working on a system. In this paper, therefore, an institutional arrangements, socio-demographic, public health education, targets and achievements are described amidst a survey conducted in whole of Bihar.

Key words: *Public Health Administration in Bihar; Public Health System; System of Medicine; Health and Development.*

1. Introduction:

Public health administration is a governmental organized attempt to improve the health of communities. Having certain territorial implications it usually involves with public health planning, financing, management, data, workforce, research, education, and laws. In a defined territory, its various functions included but not limited to demography, epidemiology, surveillance, preparedness, health informatics, public health data, food-drug-blood safety, and ensuring various public health services and programs. Therefore, this particular study investigated the *Public Health Administration* in Bihar during September 2013 to September 2015.

2. Statement of problem:

There were discussions about improvements in the public health sector of Bihar, since inception of the *National Rural Health Mission* in the year 2005. Bihar is included among one of the eight Empowered Action Group (EAG) high focused states. In the year 1957, only 33 percent of the population had physical access to any public health services and that figure still stood around 34 percent as this study has also found. The problem would appear enormous, considering a situation that existed in Bihar that almost 230 women die delivering child every 100000 live births, similarly almost 43 newborn babies die per 1000 live births in a year, and even further to make thing worse another 60 children per 1000 live births were having the probability of dying prior completing fifth birth anniversary. Further, only 37 percent of total pregnancies were able to receive full antenatal care, any skilled workforce attended only 47 percent births, and just 31 percent of the total population was using improved sanitation.

Public health practices are fast becoming more and more oriented towards the society. Regular community and home visits by doctors or paramedics still eluded millions of children, women, disabled, and old age persons. The visible problems such as an increased burden of diseases, lack of parity in access, low coverage, quality compromises, and lack of regularity were in fact never appropriately quantified with logical inferences and causes. There was very little research at the university levels over various public health issues. There was a gap and a lack of information, literature and knowledge with their integration.

3. Aims and objectives:

There were two main objectives, the research objectives, and the capacity building objectives. The research objectives

included collection of new data on public health coverage, parity in access, quality of health care, cost, and rural - urban gap in the public health sector. The aim was also to investigate the institutional arrangement and functioning of the public health system in Bihar, with specifically studying the workforce status, demography, epidemiology, data management, public health laws, policies, planning, process, financing, and mandatory compliance, such as medico-legal, citizen charter, blood, food, and drug safety. The objectives were to integrate the scattered knowledge, literature, and information.

Under the capacity building objective research scholar completed 3 short term courses and training. A course titled *Health Research Fundamentals* offered jointly by the *ICMR School of Public Health* and *National Institute of Epidemiology, Chennai*; a course on *Biostatistics and Design of Experiments*, offered online by the *Indian Institute of Technology, Chennai*; and a four month internet based course on *Remote Sensing and GIS* by the *Indian Remote Sensing Institute, Dehradun (ISRO)*, were successfully completed. A ten days research methodology training under the aegis of ICSSR at A. N. Sinha Institute, Patna was also completed successfully.

The study with fellowship provided opportunities to interact with different students, teachers, and scholars. Papers were presented at the *ICMR National Seminar on Public Health data*. Articles were published in the *Indian Journal of Applied & Clinical Sociology*. Research scholar also advanced his teaching abilities at PG levels.

4. Research questions:

The study primarily pursued following main research questions:-

Q 1. How the *Public Health Administration* in Bihar was structured and functioned?

Q 2. How *Public Health Administration* in Bihar delivered?

Q 3. What were *public health objectives* and achievements in Bihar?

5. Methodology:

The overall research adopted a mixed methods involved with qualitative, quantitative, and empirical methods. Qualitative methods involved with survey of literature & secondary data, case studies, and interviews. The quantitative methods used

mathematical and not statistical, and involved with estimation of public health coverage, gap analysis of a number of public health facilities and workforce. The empiricism was based upon research scholar own work experience and observations that enhanced his analytical abilities.

Survey of health facilities and institutions was preferred over survey of beneficiaries or population. The survey of beneficiaries or the population was not considered good for such kind of surveys because such information would have a time interval between the services received by the beneficiary and time of survey. Even, certainly yes and no at one place or another would not represent the entire gamut or phenomena. Because, a *Public Health Administration* is not just about the delivery of services, rather it also included the capacity, arrangement, environment, and overall preparedness. Nevertheless, at several instances information were retrieved from various beneficiaries about the access, timing, satisfaction, and deficiencies.

A comparative aspect of desirable and existing public health practices was worked upon. It provided the distinction between the desired and delivered public health services. Therefore, a survey of 193 public health institutions, organizations, and facilities of Bihar were accomplished under this study.

The distinct geography and demography was considered in selecting a particular health facility. To capture respective information from different facilities, institutions, and levels or functionaries, two different sets of questionnaire were used.

6. Findings:

The main findings included structural deficiencies resulting in functional inaccuracies, a decline of institutional control, and core public health objectives not achieved or delayed what may have been achieved. The core findings therefore may be summarized as follows:-

6.1 Surveillance, epidemiology, and demography:

There was tremendous data gap on disease prevalence and burden. Almost 85 percent of the total Bihar population lived in villages. Nearly 58 percent were below the age of 25 years, the highest proportion in India. There were almost 14 major cities in Bihar having population around 0.2 million or more. The state capital Patna was the most populous city in Bihar having a population of more than 2 million.

The demographic pattern of Bihar was more similar to the *Contemporary* or *Delayed Epidemiological Transition Model* where morality rate and fertility rate both declining slowly but steadily. However, it was apposite to the *Classical Epidemiological Transition Model* that applied to most developed countries. The total population of Bihar as per 2011 census was 100.38 million with a decade growth rate of 23 percent against 25.07 percent previously measured. The best sex ratio in Bihar at birth was exhibited by districts like *Buxar*, *Aurangabad* and *Banka* that measured at 997, 985 and 978 respectively by the *Annual Health Survey Report* for the year 2011-12 while the lowest sex ratio at birth was recorded for districts like *Kaimur* and *Purnea* at 871 and 878 respectively during the same period. The mean age of marriage in Bihar was estimated at 23.5 years.

The estimated number of people suffering from any kind of disabilities per 100000 populations was 1617. The number of injured persons per 100000 populations was estimated at 231 out of that 198 suffered from major injuries.

6.2 Morbidity and Mortality:

There were no integrated system to record and present data on all morbidity and mortality in Bihar. Therefore, such data presented may not be realistic. However, as per state health information system during 2012-13 the number of persons suffered from diarrhea/dysentery, Acute Respiratory Infections, fever of all types, and others types of acute illness was estimated at 1900, 4199, 7421, and 14178 respectively out of that a total of 98.2 percent expected to get treatment. However, the percentage of people taking treatment at government health facilities was estimated at just 4.8 percent that could term extremely low. Per 100000 populations almost 12003 people suffered from any chronic illness. 354 people were diabetic, 757 suffered from hypertension, 330 infected with Tuberculosis, 117 suffered from Asthma or Chronic Respiratory Diseases. However, just 49.5 percent people got treated out of which only 8.5 percent got treated from any governmental facilities. The percentage of pregnancies involving women aged 15-49 years resulted in abortion was estimated at 5 percent. It was needed to develop a system to record all morbidities and mortalities in the state.

6.3 Public health laws:

A range of laws was in force for practice, conduct, trials, sale, storage, administration of drugs, training, medical research, ethical treatment of animals, the safety of patients and medical professionals. In addition, laws related to labor, human rights, citizen charter, gender nondiscrimination, and work place prevention for patients and women were applied in the public health sector of Bihar. Most of those laws listed in the main thesis.

6.4 Entities for public health:

To promote the *public health services*, a separate department headed by a Cabinet Minister/ Chief Minister was set up in Bihar having one secretariat, one directorate, and nine regional directorates. In addition, there were public health institutes, family planning institutes, and Aids Control Society, and organization, laboratories for food, drug, and blood safety.

There was a State Health Society, Bihar at the state level, headed by Chief Minister, and 36 District Health Societies at the district levels headed by District magistrates and Civil Surgeons. In addition, *Rogi Kalyan Samitis* were constituted for primary health centres, community health centres, first referral units, district hospitals, and medical college hospitals. The Secretariat along with an attached directorate with nine regional directorates was functioning in the state.

6.5 Infrastructure and workforce:

The overall public health care in Bihar is extended through 9696 Health Sub Centers, 1360 Additional Primary Health Centers, 534 Primary Health Centers, 466 Community Health Center, 55 Sub Divisional Hospitals, 36 District Hospitals, and 13 Medical Colleges & Hospitals. Railway Hospitals were in

Patna, Hazipur, Saran, and Katihar. There were Army Hospitals functioning at *Danapur, Gaya, and North Bihar.* An ESI Hospitals were functioning at Patna including a medical college at *Bihta.*

Despite all those facilities it was estimated under this survey that a total of 20760 Health Sub Centers, 3460 Additional Primary Health Centers, 865 Referral Hospital or Community Health Centers, 63 Sub-Divisional Hospitals, 38 District/Sadar like Hospitals were required in Bihar as per population norms of the Indian Public Health Standards (IPHS). In addition, another 21 Medical Colleges & Hospitals were needed in Bihar.

Almost 16943 Female Health Workers/ ANMs are positioned at the all-9696 functional Health Sub Centres in Bihar. This number also included those workers posted at different Primary and Additional Primary Centres in the State. A total number of 1074 Male Health Workers are positioned at different 9696 Health Sub Centres. A total number of 358 Female Health Assistant /LHV is posted at different PHCs. The numbers of Health Assistant Male at PH Cs were 556. 3532 Doctors were posted at PH Cs. In addition, 451 General duty medical officers (GDMOs) and 80 Block extension educators (BEE) positioned at PHCs. The numbers of PHCs/APHCs functional in Bihar with four, three, two, and one doctor were respectively measured at 421, 32, 62, and 1330 whereas 18 APHCs were without any doctor. Lady Doctors were deployed at only 165 PHCs. 212 PHCs were without any pharmacist. However, in 1384 PHCs/APHCs AYUSH facilities are created. Only 41 surgeons positioned at CHCs in Bihar and there was a shortfall of 29 such surgeons. Likewise, at CHC level, it was a shortfall of 31 Obstetricians and Gynecologists as they are functioning only at 39 CHCs. Physicians, Pediatricians, and Radiographers are deployed at only 28, 43, and 13 CHCs respectively.

6.6 Services & coverage:

This survey has its own estimate that the public health coverage in Bihar was around 34 percent and not improved since 1957. The public health services in Bihar have been extended to all citizens irrespective of caste, religion, and income level. Any special arrangements, such as health insurance, funds for institutional deliveries had benefited only to below the poverty line or BPL families. BPL families could also avail several paid services such as ambulatory, diagnostics, and other paid services either entirely free or at reasonable rates.

The Out Patient and Inpatient Department services were largely free of cost at most public health facilities, however, at some place a lower amount has been charged as registration amount. An amount of Rs. 5/- and Rs. 10/- are charged as registration amount at several hospitals including Medical College Hospitals.

However, home care services, services for old age persons, medicinal guarantee of all kinds, diagnostics of all kinds, mental health, dental and physical therapy services, and health services for war veterans were not insured. Likewise, the AYUSH was not adequately functional at any location in Bihar. No ambulatory services, surgical facilities, free medicines and foods were available in regular manner one

could find at any sub district hospitals. Major diagnostics, pathology, ultrasound, MRI, CT were not ensured at most district hospitals and FRUs.

2.4 million Vials of anti-rabies vaccines usually consumed annually in Bihar costing approximately Rupees 300 crores at current rates. Such huge wastage could have been limited by checking and quarantining stray dogs and monkeys. If the municipalities had functioned well in all the districts then some water borne and vector borne diseases may have been also restricted and such failures caused numerous damage to life and economics. A health care system must allow individuals to choose their specialist for out-of-hospital care. However, most of time patients are compelled to visit doctors not wished with them. There was not any facility for after-hours care at any public health centre in Bihar. In many countries of world doctor agrees to participate on a roster to provide appropriate after-hours medical care to people in the territory. The National Palliative Care program also not started in the country. Mental health care largely ignored in Bihar, especially in the public sector. It was required to set up a dedicated mental hospital in Bihar since only such kind of hospital situated at Kanke, Ranchi now went to Jharkhand state due to state's reorganization in the year 2000. A variety of mental health care services including non-specialized services and specialized services are required through psychiatrists, psychologists, community-based mental health services, psychiatric hospitals, psychiatric units within general acute hospitals, and residential care facilities. Despite all claims no specialized healthcare facilities such as kidney, liver and other organ transplant functioned regularly and adequately at any Specialty or super Specialty hospitals. People suffered and waited long even for dialysis. Even diabetes and cardiac care were not so streamlined at any district or sub district hospitals.

6.7 Health insurance:

Under the *National Health Insurance Scheme*, almost 7 million families were covered. The overall expenditure on this scheme was estimated at Rs. 2500 crore annually and Bihar Government was paying an amount of Rs. 82 crore per annum. During 2014-15, Bihar government had allocated an amount of Rs.57 crore in this regard. Eight insurance companies were engaged in this scheme. The Cholamandalam General Insurance Company was extending this service in *Begusarai, Khagadia, Araria, East Champaran, Katihar, Munger and Patna.* United India Insurance extended services in *Jeahanabad, Purnea, Saharasa, Kishanganj, Arwal, and Bhagalpur.* ICICI Lombard in *Samastipur, Banka, Sheikhpura, Siwan, Chapra, Madhepura, Nalanda and Muzaffarpur* districts. Tata AIA extended services in *Bhojpur, West Champaran, Gaya, and Supaul* districts. Apollo Munich in *Darbhanga, Sheohar and Vaishalli* districts. HDFC Argo in *Kaimur, Buxar, Aurangabad, and Rohtas* districts. MAX Bopa in *Madhubani and Gopaganj* districts. Reliance operated in *Sitamarhi* district. Under the scheme, a Smart Card provided to the head of the each family after realizing a contribution of Rs. 30 only. The Smart Card accepted in almost 400 government and private listed hospitals in Bihar. Free diagnostics, treatments, and medicines ensured.

Health insurance schemes in Bihar not adequately regulated in Bihar and still very low in coverage. There were several irregularities have been reported in Bihar from different areas. The government may think paying full, part, or subsidized premiums.

6.8 Public health financing:

The state government has earmarked Rs 5,085 crore for health-related facilities in the financial year 2012-13, up from around Rs 1,000 crore that it was spending in 2005-06. Moreover, the government has planned to spend up to 2.5 percent on health services against the current expenditure of 1.2 percent of the GDP. For the year 2013-14 expenditure for health sector is estimated at Rs. 3356.84 crore as against Rs 3085.99 crore for the year 2012-13. During the year provision of a higher amount of Rs 270.85 crore over the previous year has been made. For the year 2013-14 the total amount included Rs 2317.62 crore Non plan, and Rs 1039.22 crore Plan scheme, include Rs 629.23 crore under State Plan and Rs 409.99 crore for Centrally Sponsored Scheme.

Nongovernmental sources provided almost 0.9 percent of health expenditure in 2010–11, including out-of-pocket spending (mostly spent on medications, dental services, aids and appliances). Private health insurance (PHI) offered a choice among private hospitals, private care in public hospitals, in-hospital specialists, and practitioners of ancillary services such as dental care, optometry, and complementary medicine. They also offered a choice in the timing of procedures. Private insurers had been able to cover out-of-hospital services. Private health insurance accounted for 7.6 percent of total health expenditure in 2010–11, and almost 2.78 percent of the population had private hospital insurance and 4.9 percent had general treatment coverage including ancillary services. *Public health administration* in Bihar failed to explore alternate avenues for financial support.

6.9 Quality care:

For quality in health care certain set of standards are required with respect to infrastructure, logistics, and workforce. Most of the medical and paramedical workforce usually study protocols as part of their curriculum. Two sets of standards practiced in the public health sector of Bihar. First was the *Bureau of Indian Standards* and the second was the *Indian Public Health Standards*. Under the *National Rural Health Mission*, the norms of *Indian Public Health Standards* applied after 2006.

There were quality control committees at several levels. It was required to set up a national or a state level commission on Safety and Quality in Health Care to provide quality cares a statutory status. They could publicly report on the safety and quality of health care performance against national standards, disseminate knowledge, identify policy directions, and develop and promote programs. An authority was needed to monitor the functioning of health service providers against standards set out. There is no any provision for compensation for patients in case he/she gets any substandard and low quality services and suffered damage to life and health.

Although there have been provisions of quality control committee in each public health hospital, nevertheless for

adequate quality control in health care system accreditation system considered extremely useful. Considering this fact a national level accreditation system was in place, namely “*National Accreditation Board of Health Care System*”, (*NABH*) constituted, however, as of June 2014, no any public hospital in Bihar could accredit. In fact the overall effort of the state government was to get accredited at least two hospitals and they have selected Sub Divisional Hospital of *Danapur* and District Hospital *Buxar*. Both hospitals still not provided accreditation.

6.10 Health disparities:

A greater degree of health disparities persisted in Bihar in terms of economic and regional levels. Those disparities were reflected in terms of existing and required number of medical, paramedical staff, a number of health facilities, and availability of infrastructure and logistics to the tune of *Indian Public Health Standards*. Some new districts like *Aurangabad*, *Lakhisarai*, *Sheohar*, *Sheikhpura*, *Jehanabad*, and *Arwal* had the lowest gap in terms of existing and required primary/additional primary health centre measured at 13, 11, 7, 5, 2, and 0 respectively. Again new districts like *Sheohar*, *Sheikhpura*, and *Arwal* had the minimum gap in number of existing and required health sub centres respectively measured at 31, 41, and 78. Such a gap was larger in districts like *Patna*, *East Champaran*, and major urban areas.

6.11 Electronic health records:

One of the core weaknesses has been also the non-availability and access of electronic health records. Although it talked vigorously about such things, however, there was no progress in this regard despite all talks.

6.12 Cost control:

In government hospitals cost should be controlled by the philosophy of an entirely free of cost, health services and it does not mean that services if free would not be available. The free services must be available also without quality compromises and in regular manner. For this sake government provided financial allocations to all health centres for expenditure on salary, establishment, infrastructure, logistics, and medicines.

A mechanism of minimum charges is introduced whereby no service provider could charge more than fixed charges. The arrangement seems good at first glance, however, there were several overriding practices.

India has so far not turned into a mature generic pharmaceuticals market like many other countries. The Government has become a near-monopolist purchaser of patent medicines which, combined with tight prescribing requirements, allows it to control pharmaceutical pricing. However, private hospitals not regulated over the price it charges for rendering services. Many private hospitals used to charge an amount that mostly turn unbearable for economically weaker person and that required capping. Diagnostics arrangements are also costly and in government hospital, there is long queue or waiting list for some diagnostics resulting in massive discomfort to patients requiring urgent treatments.

6.13 Health information management system:

A health information system was operated by the State Health Society, Bihar as a part of the national level *Health Information Management System*. The lack of geographical information and data management protocol was major deficiency in this area. There were no provisions for direct data upload by health facilities. It also required measuring and presenting information on disease frequency, prevalence, incidence, and case fatality for different diseases among the target population.

6.14 Medical education:

The ten present medical colleges were extremely short in comparison of several states and in terms of a massive population of Bihar. In addition, *Medical Council of India* time to time kept coming up with several shortcomings resulting in no increase of medical seats in medical colleges and non-grant of admissions from fresh batches.

Some of the most common and specific drawbacks highlighted by *Medical Council of India* (MCI) in Bihar Medical Colleges usually included: Lack of Professors, Associate Professors, Assistant Professors, Tutors, and, Residents, Paramedic, and other staff, lack of infrastructure such as galleried study room, common room, hostel, bath and toilet facilities and also library facilities. Non-computerization of medical data emerged as one of the major weaknesses in Bihar Medical colleges. Some other drawbacks noticed were such as lack of Pharmacy Vigilant Committees, the lack of an e - class, photography units.

The total MBBS seats available in Bihar were almost 1000 one of the lowest in the country. Even at the post graduate or at MD or MS level, number of seats was negligible considering the population.

6.15 Signs of improvements:

Several health indicators in Bihar have improved significantly over the last 10 years because there was considerable downward movement in infant mortality rate, maternal mortality rate, sex ratio, whereas there was a significant increase in the number of IPD/OPD cases, institutional deliveries, and ambulatory services. No polio cases reported for the last four successive years, however, it required to sustain the efforts because polio reemerged in 28 countries where it declared eliminated. The OPD cases have increased from a level of 39 per PHC per month to a level of almost over 1000 per month. The immunization coverage has increased from a level of almost 28 percent to over 60 percent. There was marked improvement in ambulatory and referral services. Institutional delivery in Bihar was estimated at 51.9 percent out of that 36.7 and 15.1 percent delivered at governmental and private institutions respectively. Mothers who did not receive any post-natal care were estimated as 20.7 percent. 35.2 percent pregnant women provided assistance under Janani *Suraksha Yojna*. 61.5 percent registered in Bihar. *Rogi Kalyan Samiti* constituted at all district hospitals, PHCs, CHCs and FRUs. Over 0.8 lakh ASHA appointed in Bihar and almost 2400 new doctors added to the system. Three new medical colleges are in process to begin.

7 Discussions:

Under the premises of previously mentioned findings, the research questions thereon can be discussed. Now let discuss the first research question that *how the Public Health Administration in Bihar was structured and functioned*. At the mental level, it could be easily hypothesized that the *Public Health Administration* in Bihar was neither structured and nor it functioned expectedly and the hypothesis turned valid because a range of structure required for implementing core public health functions such as public health data, vital registration, civil registration, medico-legal, blood, food and drug safety, epidemiology, and surveillance were missing. The demographic functions of varied types including medical demography could not be implemented because of just one demographer at the state level. No public health units, epidemiological, and surveillance units were functional at most districts of Bihar. The workforce deficiency was massive in terms of specialist and super specialists. Medical colleges lacked all grades of teachers. People were seen wandering at public health facilities for medico legal services, especially postmortem reports, injury reports, and fitness, sickness, and disablement certificates. There was a lack of synergy in the creation of infrastructure, availability of workforce. At several places infrastructure and logistics not utilized due to lack of workforce. Existing workforce required orientation and multi Skilling to perform several schedules due to changed technology. Number of medical colleges, institutes, and number of seats in existing institutes not increased. Those all symptoms existed mainly due to lack of public health leadership, knowledge, structural, and functional failures. Lack of workforce of various kinds at various levels was evident that contributed *structural and functional* disablement. The overall *public health administrative* structure in Bihar could not be termed as a *mature organization* because of more bureaucratic orientations, and less flexible and boundaries less approaches. It needed to restructure the entire set up according to the various *public health functions*. Several those structural failures could have been avoided by implementing administrative reforms, however, that needed knowledgeable *public health leadership*.

Now taking up question number two that how *Public Health Administration in Bihar delivered*. The working hypothesis that the *Public health services in Bihar though delivered through various public health organizations, associations, and institutions, yet there was decline of public health institutions* proved valid because of the fact though there were public health institutions however, they never functioned as an institution. The reasons of those declines may be attributed mainly in terms of two reasons, redundancy of existing institutions and non-development of alternative institutions with adequate structure. Several new institutions arranged after 2005 however, they were mostly like a temporary structure in form of societies aimed at anyhow doing certain tasks and that's not improved the institutional control. Institutions demanded leaderships however, due to development economy persuaded have compelled the state government to allow the developmental approach in the public health sector. Such approaches also adopted in other social sectors including education. The focus of such approaches was to anyhow improve some macro developmental indicators in a short

period, however, that not worked and lacked sustainability. Workforce employed on a contractual basis and that created tensions between permanent and contract staff.

Bihar is also known for political and administrative meddling of various types in the form of transfer, posting, and recruiting neglecting core public health function requirements. More and more people wanted to be posted on or near to urban areas and hesitated in getting posted in remote or rural areas. The laboratory for drug, food, and blood safety remained redundant for many years. Quality and cost control not effectively implemented and even their committee meeting also not regularly and meaningfully organized. In addition, reckless privatization and outsourcing of the public health services also caused a decline in control. Private practice by government doctors could be another example of fall of institutional control.

The third and final question, that *what were public health objectives and achievements in Bihar*. The conceptualized hypothesis that the core public health objectives in Bihar were achievable, however not achieved was also remained valid. The core public health objectives for Bihar where full coverage of services with quality, cost, and regularity with parity in access. Those objectives are achievable, however not achieved due to the answers of the previous two questions. Per capita allocation of funds in Bihar was around rupees 400 per annum

and that could have been raised. A practice of developing infrastructure and logistics, according to the available workforce would have been beneficial. The failure could be also due to non-execution of dedicated public health leadership programs. Subjects like Public health, Social & Community Medicine, Public Health Management, and Public Health Leadership are not taught at universities in Bihar. There were numbered academic researchers in those areas. Therefore, the core public health objectives in Bihar were achievable yet not achieved or delayed.

8. Conclusion:

Failing the public health provisions in Bihar was mainly due to *structural* and *functional* deficiencies of the *public health organizations* and *institutions*. It caused decline in institutional control and the core public health objective that could have been achieved was not achieved or delayed.

9. Scope for future research:

The causes of structural, functional, and institutional decline could be many. The various causes may be involved with systems of medicine, health market, workforce, leadership, and technology. In addition, all these may also get affected by the local social-political, cultural, economic, and leadership issues. Therefore, it required proper study of these various factors and their dynamics.
